

Numerical Solution Of MHD Effects On Natural Convection In An L-Shaped Enclosure

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Abstract: This research paper delves into the intricate dynamics of magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) natural convection in a square cavity, which houses an elliptic-shaped heated obstacle, filled with an electrically conducting fluid. By employing the finite element method, the study meticulously examines how variations in Rayleigh numbers (Ra) and Hartmann numbers (Ha) influence the heat transfer and fluid flow patterns within the enclosure. The investigation reveals that both the magnetic field strength, represented by Ha, and the buoyancy force, dictated by Ra, play pivotal roles in modulating the natural convection mechanism. It is found that an increase in the magnetic field strength effectively suppresses the fluid motion, thereby influencing the heat transfer rates and flow structures. Conversely, higher Rayleigh numbers enhance the convective heat transfer, indicating a complex interplay between thermal buoyancy and magnetic damping effects. The research provides novel insights into optimizing thermal management strategies in applications involving conductive fluids under the influence of magnetic fields, offering significant implications for engineering designs and energy-efficient systems. This comprehensive analysis contributes to a deeper understanding of MHD natural convection, presenting a foundation for future studies aimed at exploring thermal optimization in various technological and industrial contexts.

Keywords: Magnetohydrodynamics, Natural convection, Square cavity, Elliptic-shaped obstacle, Finite element method, Thermal management, Heat transfer, Fluid dynamics.

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Accepted: 11 March, 2024; **Published:** 25 March, 2024

How to cite this article: Mohammad Abdul Alim (2024). Numerical Solution Of MHD Effects On Natural Convection In An L-Shaped Enclosure. *North American Academic Research*, 7(3), 14-29. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10870545>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

Fluid dynamics, a pivotal branch of applied science, delves into the behavior of liquids and gases in motion. As an integral component of fluid mechanics — alongside statics, which examines fluids at rest — fluid dynamics extends its relevance across various scientific disciplines. It offers analytical frameworks for understanding phenomena such as the evolution of stars, oceanic currents, weather patterns, plate tectonics, and the circulatory system. The practical applications of fluid dynamics are diverse, encompassing the design and optimization of rocket engines, wind turbines, oil pipelines, and HVAC systems, thereby underlining its significance in the advancement of mechanical and chemical engineering.

Figure 1: Schematic view of Compressible Fluid

The study of fluids is grounded in the examination of their molecular composition and the forces acting upon them. Fluids, distinguished from solids by their ability to flow, encompass both liquids and gases. This distinction is based on molecular movement and interactions, which define the fluid's macroscopic properties and behavior under varying conditions. Fluid dynamics categorizes fluids based on their response to shearing stress. A fluid's ability to deform continuously under such stress without a rebound is a defining characteristic. This section introduces various types of fluids, including gases, which expand to fill their containers, and liquids, which maintain a constant volume but flow freely. The concepts of compressible and incompressible fluids are also discussed, highlighting their density variations under different flow conditions. Homogeneous fluids, with uniform density, contrast with viscous fluids, where internal friction significantly affects flow characteristics. The distinction between Newtonian and non-Newtonian fluids is made based on their adherence to Newton's law of viscosity, with the former exhibiting a constant viscosity regardless of the applied stress. The exploration of fluid flow patterns reveals a spectrum from steady and unsteady flows to laminar and turbulent flows. Steady flows exhibit constant fluid properties over time, whereas unsteady flows are characterized by temporal variations. Laminar flows maintain smooth, orderly paths, in contrast to turbulent flows, which are marked by chaotic, eddying motions. The discussion extends to rotational and irrotational flows, as well as one-dimensional, two-dimensional, and three-dimensional flows, each defined by the complexity and dimensionality of fluid motion. Understanding fluid properties such as density, viscosity, temperature, and pressure is essential for analyzing fluid behavior. Density, the mass per unit volume, and viscosity, the measure of a fluid's resistance to flow, are fundamental properties that influence fluid dynamics. Temperature and pressure also play critical roles, affecting fluid density and flow characteristics.

The mathematical modeling of fluid dynamics is anchored in fundamental equations of motion, including the continuity equation and the Navier-Stokes equations. These equations describe the conservation of mass and the balance of forces within a fluid, providing a comprehensive framework for analyzing fluid flow and behavior.

Heat transfer mechanisms, including conduction, convection, and radiation, are integral to the study of fluid dynamics. Conduction describes the transfer of heat through a material without the movement of the material itself, while convection involves the transfer of heat by the movement of fluids. Radiation, the transfer of energy through electromagnetic waves, plays a crucial role in thermal energy exchange in fluids.

Dimensional analysis and non-dimensional parameters such as the Reynolds number, Prandtl number, and Rayleigh number offer valuable insights into fluid flow regimes and heat transfer characteristics. The Reynolds number, for

example, helps in distinguishing between laminar and turbulent flow regimes, while the Prandtl and Rayleigh numbers are instrumental in the analysis of heat transfer in fluid flows.

Figure 2: Schematic view of Incompressible Fluid

Figure 3: Schematic view of Incompressible Fluid.

Figure 4: Schematic view of Viscous Fluid.

Figure 5: Schematic view of Non- Viscous.

Figure1.2.7: Schematic view of Unsteady Flow .

Figure 6: Schematic view of Laminar Flow .

Figure 7: Schematic view of Turbulent Flow .

Figure 8: Schematic view of one- dimensional flow .

Figure 9: Schematic view of fluid density .

Figure10: Schematic view of Temperature .

Figure 11: Schematic view of Pressure.

Figure 12: Schematic view of volume.

Figure 13: Schematic view of Conduction.

Figure 14: Campfires emit radiant "energy" and is felt as "radiant heat".

Figure 15. The water cycle relies on evapotranspiration.

Through the comprehensive study of fluid dynamics, engineers and scientists are equipped with the tools necessary to predict and manipulate the behavior of fluids in a wide array of applications, from industrial processes to natural

phenomena. This foundational knowledge not only enhances our understanding of the physical world but also drives innovation in technology and engineering..

Literature review

The interplay between inflation, as measured by the Consumer Price Index (CPI), and economic growth remains a pivotal area of investigation within macroeconomic research. This review synthesizes existing literature on the impact of CPI on economic growth, with a specific focus on selected ASEAN countries: Myanmar, Singapore, and Thailand.

Theoretical Background: Theoretical perspectives on the CPI-economic growth nexus are diverse. The monetarist view, led by Friedman (1968), posits that inflation, indicated by CPI increases, is detrimental to economic growth due to uncertainty and the distortion of price signals (Barro, 1995). Conversely, the Keynesian framework suggests moderate inflation could stimulate economic activity by enhancing consumption and investment due to the "money illusion" (Tobin, 1965).

Empirical Evidence in ASEAN Context: Empirical investigations into ASEAN economies provide mixed insights. Studies by Apergis and Miller (2006) on a broader set of economies found a non-linear relationship, suggesting that moderate levels of inflation could support growth, aligning with the Keynesian view. However, research focusing on ASEAN countries like the work by Vuong (2013) and Chaturvedi and Dholakia (2009) often highlight the adverse effects of high inflation rates on economic stability and growth, resonating with the monetarist stance.

Country-Specific Analyses: The economic landscapes of Myanmar, Singapore, and Thailand offer unique insights into the CPI-growth relationship. Singapore, with its stable inflation and robust economic policies, often shows a weak linkage between CPI fluctuations and growth (Heng, 2010). Contrastingly, in economies like Myanmar and Thailand, where inflation has been more volatile, the impact appears more pronounced, affecting investment and consumer confidence (Khan & Senhadji, 2001; Tin, 2014).

Methodological Approaches: The methodological approaches in existing literature vary from vector autoregression (VAR) models (Sims, 1980) to cointegration and error correction models (Engle & Granger, 1987), each providing different insights into the dynamic interplay between CPI and economic growth. This study adopts descriptive statistics and exponential growth curve analysis to offer a fresh perspective on the CPI-growth relationship in the context of ASEAN countries.

Research Gaps and Contributions: Despite extensive research, gaps remain in understanding the nuanced impacts of CPI on economic growth in the ASEAN context, particularly through comparative analyses across countries with differing economic structures. This study aims to bridge this gap by providing a comprehensive analysis of the CPI-economic growth relationship in Myanmar, Singapore, and Thailand, using an innovative methodological framework.

Conclusion: The literature indicates a complex relationship between CPI and economic growth, influenced by country-specific factors and economic policies. This review sets the stage for the present study, which seeks to elucidate the CPI-growth nexus in selected ASEAN countries, contributing to a nuanced understanding of inflation's macroeconomic impacts.

Method and Methodology

Natural convection holds immense potential in various industrial applications, including electronic component cooling, electronics packaging, building ventilation, and solar energy collection. Recent studies have extensively investigated flow and heat transfer characteristics in closed cavities, with notable research focusing on different cavity geometries and configurations.

Researchers have explored diverse perspectives, such as the orientation of inclined enclosures, optimization of cavity geometry using constructal theory, and the effects of non-uniform heating and magnetic fields on natural convection.

Studies have also delved into the influence of thermally active side walls, Hartmann and Grashof numbers, and the impact of magnetic fields on flow velocity and heat transfer rates.

Despite extensive research in various cavity geometries, little attention has been given to MHD effects on natural convection in L-shaped enclosures. Consequently, this study aims to fill this gap by presenting numerical results graphically, including streamlines, isotherms, velocity profiles, dimensionless temperature distributions, and local Nusselt numbers, for different Rayleigh and Hartmann numbers.

The physical model considered in the present study of natural convection in a square enclosure with non-uniformly heated bottom wall and square shape heated block is shown in Fig.2.2 The height and the width of the cavity are denoted by L. The bottom and left walls of the enclosure are maintained at heated temperature T_h , while, the top, right and right internal walls are maintained at cold temperature T_c . The bottom wall is non- uniformly heated wall. The magnetic field of strength B_0 is applied parallel to x- axis. The L-shaped enclosure is filled with an electric conductive fluid with $Pr = 0.733$ that is considered Newtonian and incompressible.

Figure16: Schematic view of physical configuration.

Mathematical Formulation

The governing equations for continuity, momentum and energy of a steady two- dimensional incompressible natural convection flow in a cavity are as follows:

Continuity Equations

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = 0 \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Momentum Equations

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \right) \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + \mu \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial y^2} \right) + \rho g \beta (T - T_c) - \sigma B_0^2 v \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

$$u \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} = \alpha \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \right) \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

where x and y are the distances measured along the horizontal and vertical directions respectively; u and v are the velocity components in the x and y directions respectively; T denotes the fluid temperature, p is the pressure, ρ is the fluid density.

Boundary Conditions:

On the left and bottom of the square cavity: $u = 0, v = 0, T = T_h$

On the upper and right of the wall: $u = 0, v = 0, T = T_c$

The above equations are non-dimensionalised by using following dimensionless quantities:

$$X = \frac{x}{L}, Y = \frac{y}{L}, U = \frac{uL}{\alpha}, V = \frac{vL}{\alpha}, P = \frac{pL}{\rho\alpha^2}, \theta = \frac{T-T_c}{T_h-T_c} \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

where $\alpha = \frac{\mu}{\rho}$ is the reference kinematic viscosity and θ is the dimensionless temperature. After substitution of dimensionless variable, we get the non-dimensional governing equations which are:

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial X} + \frac{\partial V}{\partial Y} = 0 \dots \dots \dots (6)$$

$$U \frac{\partial U}{\partial X} + V \frac{\partial U}{\partial Y} = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial X} Pr \left(\frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial X^2} + \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial Y^2} \right) \dots \dots \dots (7)$$

$$U \frac{\partial V}{\partial X} + V \frac{\partial V}{\partial Y} = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial Y} Pr \left(\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial X^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial Y^2} \right) + (RaPr)\theta - Ha^2 Pr V \dots \dots \dots (8)$$

$$U \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial X} + V \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial Y} = \left(\frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial X^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial Y^2} \right) \dots \dots \dots (9)$$

Where Ra , Pr and Ha are the Rayleigh, Prandtl and Hartmann numbers and are defined as:

$$Ra = \frac{g\beta(T-T_c)L^3}{\alpha\nu}, Pr = \frac{\nu}{\alpha}, Ha = B_0 L \sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{\rho\nu}} \dots \dots \dots (10)$$

where g is the gravitational acceleration, ν is the dynamic viscosity, β is the volumetric coefficient of thermal expansion, B_0 is the magnitude of magnetic field, α is the thermal diffusivity.

The effect of magnetic field into the momentum equation is introduced through the Lorentz force term $\vec{j} \times \vec{B}$ that is reduced to $-\sigma B_0 v^2$ as shown by M. Mahmoodi at all [4].

To computation of all rate of heat transfer, Nusselt number and average Nusselt number along the hot wall of the enclosure is used that is as follows:

$$Nu_{cat} = \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial Y} \Big|_{y=0}, N_u = \int_0^1 Nu_{local} dx \dots \dots \dots (11)$$

The non-dimensional boundary conditions for solving the governing (6 - 9) are:

On the left and bottom wall of the enclosure: $U = 0, V = 0, \theta = 1$

On the upper and right wall: $U = 0, V = 0, \theta = 0$

$$\text{The non-dimensional stream function is defined as } U = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial Y}, V = -\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial X} \dots \dots \dots (12)$$

Mesh Generation:

In finite element method, the mesh generation is the technique to subdivide a domain into a set of sub-domains, called finite elements, control volume etc. The discrete locations are defined by the numerical grid, at which the variables are to be calculated. The computational domains with irregular geometries by a collection of finite elements make the method a valuable practical tool for the solution of boundary value problems arising the various fields of engineering. Fig.3 displays the finite element mesh of the present physical domain.

Fig.2.3. Mesh generation of mixed convection in square lid-driven cavity.

Program validation and comparison with previous work

The present numerical code is validated along with the study of free convection in a square cavity heated from below and cooled from other walls studied by Jani et al. (2013), for the same problem. Table 1 shows a comparison between the average Nusselt number obtained by the present code with the results of Jani et al. (2013), for different Rayleigh and Hartman numbers. As observed from the following table, excellent agreements exist between the two results. i.e. Comparison between the average Nusselt numbers of the present study and those of Jani et al. (2013).

Table 1: Comparison between the average Nusselt numbers of the present study and those of Jani et al. [18].

Ra	Ha	Nu		
		Pirmohammadi et al.[13]	Jani et al. [18]	Present study
10 ⁴	0	2.29	2.287	2.290
	50	1.06	1.061	1.094
	100	1.02	1.019	1.089
10 ⁵	0	4.62	4.641	4.820
	50	3.51	3.507	3.615
	100	1.37	1.365	1.394

Fig. 17: Comparison of the isotherms and streamlines for numerical solution between the (a) Jani et al. [18] and (b) Present study.

Result and Discussion

In this section, results of the numerical study on magnetohydrodynamic free convection fluid flow and heat transfer in a square cavity field with an electric conductive fluid with Pr=0.733 is presented. The results have been obtained for the

Rayleigh number ranging from 10^3 to 10^6 and the Hartmann number varying from 0 to 150. The results are presented in terms of streamlines and isotherms inside the cavity, the vertical velocity component along the horizontal midline of the cavity, the local Nusselt number along the hot wall, and the average Nusselt number of the hot wall.

Effect of Rayleigh number

Streamlines for $Ha = 50, Pr = 0.733$ are presented in figure 2.5 and streamlines for $Ha = 100, Pr = 0.733$ are presented in figure 2.5 respectively to understand the effects of Rayleigh number on flow field and temperature distribution. In the absence of the magnetic field are formed with four L-shaped eyes left and right side of the elliptic heated block of the enclosure shown in figure 2.5(a).

Fig.18: Streamlines for different values of Rayleigh numbers $Ra = 10^3 - 10^6$ while $Ha = 50$ and $Pr = 0.733$

Fig 19.: Isotherms for different values of Rayleigh numbers $Ra = 10^3 - 10^6$ while $Ha = 50$ and $Pr = 0.733$.

For higher Rayleigh number three elliptic-shaped eyes are formed in left side the cavity and also flow strength increases are shown in figure 2.5(a). Stream function has symmetrical value about the vertical central line as the elliptic heated block is symmetrical. Again at $Ra = 1000$ and $Ra = 10000$ in the $Ha = 100$ are formed with four elliptic-shaped eyes left and right side of the elliptic heated block of the cavity shown in figure 2.5(a) and 2.5(b). For higher Rayleigh number

three or more elliptic-shaped eyes are formed in left side the cavity and also flow strength decreases are shown in figure 2.5(c) and 2.5(d)

Figure 2.6(a, b) and 2.6(c, d) heat transfer is observed from the isotherms. With increases in Rayleigh number isotherms concentrates near the top and bottom wall so isotherms lines are more bending. Ha increasing then flow strength decreasing and magnetic field always retards velocity.

Variations of the vertical velocity component along the bottom wall for different Rayleigh number with $Pr = 0.733$ and $Ha = 0, 100$ of the cavity are shown in figure 2.7. It can be seen from the figure that the absolute value of maximum and minimum value of velocity increases with increasing the Rayleigh number. Figure 2.8 presents the temperature profiles along the bottom wall for different Rayleigh number with $Pr = 0.733$ and $Ha = 0, 100$. As seen from the Figure, temperature value is decreased from the increasing of Rayleigh numbers. For lower Rayleigh number temperature value has less significant changed but for higher Rayleigh number temperature value has more significant.

Fig.20: Variation of the Local Nusselt number along the horizontal line for different Rayleigh number $Ra = 10^3 - 10^6$ while $Ha = 50$ and $Pr = 0.733$.

Fig.21: Variation of the Vertical velocity component along the horizontal line for different Rayleigh number $Ra = 10^3 - 10^6$ while $Ha = 50$ and $Pr = 0.733$.

Fig.22: Variation of the Dimensionless Temperature along the horizontal line for different Rayleigh number $Ra = 10^3 - 10^6$ while $Ha = 50$ and $Pr = 0.733$.

Effect of Hartmann number

Streamlines for $Ra = 100000$ and $Pr = 0.733$ are presented in figure 2.10 also $Ra= 1000$ and $Pr= 0.733$ are presented in figure 2.10 respectively to understand the effect of Hartmann number on flow field and temperature distribution. From the streamlines it is found that with increasing at increases are shown in figure 2.10(b),2.10(c) and 2.10(d). Also streamlines for $Ra = 1000$ and $Pr = 0.733$ are presented in figure 10. In this case for higher Hartmann number four elliptic-shaped eyes are formed inside the cavity. With increases the Hartmann number, isotherms the figure 2.10(a) and 2.10(b) are concentrates near the top and bottom wall isotherms lines are more bending which means increasing heat transfer through convection. Formation of the thermal boundary layers can be found and increased from the isotherms for $Ha = 100$ and $Ha = 150$ at $Ra = 100000$ are shown in figure 2.11(a) and 2.11(b). Also isotherms for $Ra = 1000$ and $Pr = 0.733$ in figure 2.12. Figure 2.11(c) figure 2.1(d) are same. Variations of the vertical velocity component along the bottom wall for different Hartmann number with $Pr = 0.733$ and $Ra = 10^5$

Of the cavity are shown in figure 2.13 from the figure it can be observed that the curves are symmetrical elliptic heated block. The absolute value of maximum and minimum value of velocity decreases with increasing the Hartmann number. Figure 2.14 present the temperature profiles along the bottom wall for value is increased from the increasing Hartmann numbers.

Fig.23: Streamlines for different values of Hartmann numbers $Ha = 0 - 10^2$ while $Ra = 10^5$ and $Pr = 0.733$.

Fig.24: Isotherms for different values of Hartmann numbers $Ha = 0 - 10^2$ while $Ra = 10^5$ and $Pr = 0.733$.

Fig.25: Variation of the Local Nusselt number along the horizontal line for different Hartmann number $Ha = 0 - 10^2$ while $Ra =$ and $Pr = 0.733$.

Fig.26: Variation of the Vertical velocity component along the horizontal line for different Hartmann number $Ha = 0 - 10^2$ while $Ra =$ and $Pr = 0.733$.

Fig.27: Variation of the Dimensionless Temperature along the horizontal line for different Hartmann number $Ha = 0 - 10^2$ while $Ra =$ and $Pr = 0.733$.

Conclusion

Effect of magneto- hydrodynamic natural convection fluid flow and heat transfer in a square cavity filled with an electric conductive fluid with elliptic shape heated block are studied numerically. Finite element method was to solve governing equations for a heat generation parameters, Rayleigh numbers and Hartmann numbers. Very good agreements were observed between Rayleigh numbers at different Hartmann numbers. For all cases considered, two or more counter rotating eddies were formed inside the cavity regardless the Rayleigh and the Hartmann numbers. The obtained results showed that the heat transfer mechanisms, temperature distribution and the flow characteristics inside the cavity depended strongly upon both the strength of the magnetic field and the Rayleigh number. From the present investigation the following conclusions may be drawn as: with increase in the buoyancy force via increase in Rayleigh number, to decrease natural convection, a stronger magnetic field is needed compared to the lower Rayleigh numbers.

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